

Impact of high-yielding varieties on rice production in Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil

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New varieties released in southern Brazil since 1970 (see table) are mostly short-statured and adapted to climatic

conditions. The harvest index has increased and yield potential, grain quality, and adaptability have promoted farmer acceptance.

Among the varieties, Bluebelle and BR-IRGA409 are early, BR-IRGA410 and BR-IRGA411 are medium duration, and BR-IRGA407 is late maturing. Breeding programs have focused on yield improvement, grain

quality, cold tolerance, and disease resistance. High yielders with durations of 109-147 d were identified and isolated. Early and medium-duration varieties were selected indirectly.

In 1984, high-yielding rice varieties represented about 98% of 704,000 ha in Rio Grande do Sul, with yields of 4.5 t/ha. BR-IRGA lines alone covered about 70% of this area. *ℒ*

High-yielding varieties released in Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil, 1970-85.

Variety	Origin	Cross-combination	Released		Approximate yield (t/ha)	Maturity (d)	Grain type ^b	Height (cm)	Area planted 1983/84 season (thousand ha)
			By ^a	Year					
Bluebelle	USA	CI 9122/Century Patna 231/CI 92 14	IPEAS	1970	4.7	109	LS	91	195.1
IRGA 407	Brazil	Selected from local variety	EEA/IRGA	1971	4.3	147	LB	130	3.1
BR-IRGA 409	CIAT/IRRI	P790-B4-4-1T (IR930-2/IR665-31-1-4)	EMBRAPA/IRGA	1978	6.1	110	LS	100	457.6
BR-IRGA 410	CIAT/IRRI	P798-B4-4-1T (IR930-53/IR665-31-2)	EMBRAPA/IRGA	1980	6.7	130	LS	110	35.2
BR-IRGA 411	Brazil	Dawn/IRGA407	EMBRAPA/IRGA	1985	4.1	130	LS	103	-

^aIPEAS = South Agricultural Research Institute now EMBRAPA; EEA = IRGA's Experimental Station; IRGA = Rio-grandense Rice Institute; EMBRAPA = Federal Agricultural Research System. ^bLS = long slender; LB = long bold.

Rice strain R243-3223 promising for lowland rainfed conditions in eastern Madhya Pradesh, India

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Agronomic conditions in Madhya Pradesh limit the adoption of typical semidwarf varieties. These conditions include dependence on the monsoon, with only 20% irrigation coverage; broadcast crop establishment, which gives low plant populations despite high seed rates; predominance of long duration varieties, which often suffer from failure of September rains; low fertilizer consumption; and lack of varieties with multiple resistance.

Breeding objectives have been modified toward developing semitall varieties of shorter duration that respond to moderate levels of fertilizer and are tolerant of commonly occurring

Table 1. Yield of R243-3223 and IR36 in Madhya Pradesh, India.

Location	Strain	Yield (t/ha)			
		1982	1983	1984	Mean
Waraseoni	R243	4.0	4.1	4.3	4.1
	IR36	3.7	3.7	2.2	3.2
Rewa	R243	4.0	2.9	2.4	3.1
	IR36	2.3	2.8	2.7	2.6
Bagwai	R243	3.7	2.9	3.3	3.3
	IR36	3.7	2.2	3.5	3.1
Raipur (Pathology)	R243	5.9	5.0	4.7	5.2
	IR36	5.8	4.9	4.4	5.0
Raipur (Breeding)	R243	3.4	3.0	2.6	3.0
	IR36	3.2	3.1	2.8	3.1
Jagdalpur	R243	4.4	4.5	6.1	5.0
	IR36	5.0	2.7	5.8	4.5
Jabalpur	R243	2.5	4.3	3.6	3.5
	IR36	3.4	4.2	3.3	3.6
Bilaspur	R243	-	-	4.0	4.0
	IR36	-	-	3.5	3.5
Mean	R243	4.0	3.8	3.8	3.9
	IR36	3.9	3.4	3.5	3.6

diseases and pests.

A new rice strain R243-3223 (IET8756) was derived from the cross IR36/IR2053-521. Cross IR7516 was received from IRRI in the F₂. This

strain has given higher yields than IR36 and Safrí 17, the most popular semidwarf and tall varieties of the region (Table 1). Its 100 ± 10 cm stature results in better germination capacity under

Table 2. Reactions^a of R243-3223, IR36, and 3 other varieties to bacterial leaf blight, blast, sheath rot, and gall midge. Madhya Pradesh, India.

Strain or variety	Mean score			Blast ^c 1983	Sheath rot ^d 1983	Gall midge (% silver shoots) 1984
	Bacterial leaf blight					
	1982	1983	1984			
R243-3223	3.6	3.0	2.9	1.8	3.0	4.0
IR36	4.7	5.0	5.3	—	—	6.8
TNI	7.0	7.2	8.9	5.0	—	62.5
Jaya	5.3	7.0	6.5	4.5	5.5	58.2
Safri 17	5.8	6.3	5.4	—	—	37.6

^aBy the Standard evaluation system for rice scale. ^b0 = no incidence, 9 = 51-100%. ^cMean of 4 locations: Almore, Cuttack, Ponnampet, and Semliguda. 0 = no lesions, 9 = all leaves dead. ^dMean of 2 locations: Faizabad and Pusa. 0 = no incidence, 9 = 51-100%.

broadcast sowing and higher drought tolerance than IR36. Its excellent tolerance for bacterial blight, gall midge, blast, and sheath rot makes it distinctly superior to Safri 17 (Table 2). Also, the new line is 15 d earlier than Safri 17, so that it frequently escapes terminal drought. ☞

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Performance trials of short-duration rice varieties at TNRRI

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Performance trials of short duration, high yielding rice varieties were conducted at TNRRI during 1984 kharif. Seven varieties from IRRRI, three from Tamil Nadu, and one from Sri Lanka were evaluated in a randomized block design with three replications.

Seedlings were spaced 15 cm between rows and 10 cm within rows. Fertilizer was 75-38-38 kg NPK/ha. Plots were free from insects and diseases from planting to harvest.

AD85001 and IR58 flowered earliest, 72 and 71 d after seeding (DAS). IR62

Performance of short-duration rice varieties at TRRI, India, 1984 kharif.

Variety	Source	Height (cm)	Days to 50% flowering	Yield (t/ha)
AD85001	Tamil Nadu	85	72	4.8
TKM 9	Tamil Nadu	91	86	5.8
ADT36	Tamil Nadu	93	84	4.8
BG367-4	Sri Lanka	98	82	6.0
IR36	IRRI	81	86	4.7
IR50	IRRI	89	82	4.6
IR52	IRRI	92	86	5.1
IR56	IRRI	96	82	5.3
IR58	IRRI	86	71	3.0
IR60	IRRI	92	82	5.1
IR62	IRRI	94	84	4.9
IR64	IRRI	92	86	5.1
				CD 0.3
				CV 7.5

was latest, 89 DAS. Other varieties flowered between 82 and 86 DAS. Varietal height ranged from 85 cm (AD85001) to 98 cm (BG367-4).

BC367-4, the Sri Lankan culture, yielded 6.0 t/ha, surpassing all other

varieties. IRRRI varieties IR52, IR50, IR60, and IR64 recorded more than 5 t/ha (see table). These varieties will be studied in multilocation and adaptive research trials in 1986 kharif. ☞

ACK-5, a new variety for Western Maharashtra, India

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Rice variety ACK-5, released in 1985, is derived from a cross between tall type D-6-2-2 and stable high yielding semidwarf IR8. The new variety has medium height (65 cm) and matures in 120 d. Its seed has a 20-d dormancy.

It is nonlodging, and is suitable for

Performance of ACK-5 in various trials. Maharashtra, India.

Trial	Year	Mean yield (t/ha)			% increase over check
		ACK-5	Jaya	RDN185-2	
Initial evaluation trial (ET)	1976-78	2.6	2.3	—	11.0
Multilocation trials	1983-84	4.5	—	3.9	14.0
Adaptive trials	1983	3.6	—	3.4	6.3
Cultivator fields	1984	3.4	—	3.2	7.4

direct sowing as well as transplanting. It is tolerant of moisture stress and iron chlorosis.

Its grain is short, bold, and coarse with acceptable cooking qualities, suitable for preparing flaked and puffed

rice. Yield is 4-6 t/ha under direct-sown conditions and 44.5 t/ha under transplanted conditions. Yield data in various trials are shown in the table. ACK-5 is moderately susceptible to blast and susceptible to bacterial blight. ☞